

Preparation and Characterisation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Iron(III) Phthalimide and Iron(III) Nitrilotriacetate with Oximes

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The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of mixed ligand complexes of iron(III) phthalimide and iron(III) nitrilotriacetate with salicylaldoxime (sox), α -furdioxime (fox), pyridine-2-aldoxime (pox) and benzildioxime (box).

Results and Discussion

The values of molar conductance of phthalimide complexes (Table 1) in dimethylformamide and of NTA complexes in water were 4.5–5.0 and 89.0–90.0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating their nonelectrolytic nature and the presence of two ions respectively. The values of magnetic moments of all the complexes were 5.80–5.90 B.M. at room temperature, a characteristic of high-spin octahedral complexes.

The electronic spectra of the complexes gave four bands at 14 000, 19 000, 24 800 and 28 100 cm^{-1} in the case of phthalimide complexes and at 13 900, 19 200, 24 600 and 28 000 cm^{-1} in the case of NTA complexes corresponding to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ and charge transfer transition respectively. The value of $10Dq$ corresponds to the first transition. The value of β was calculated using the relationship¹, $Dq/B = 1.1$. Thus the values of B (Racah parameter) and β were found to be 1 272 cm^{-1} and 0.98 in the case of phthalimide complexes and 1 263 cm^{-1} and 0.97 in the case of NTA complexes respectively. From these data, the values of $\pi \rightarrow T_{2g}$, $e_g \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ were calculated and found to be 10 800, 14 100 and 38 900 cm^{-1} in the case of phthalimide complexes and 10 700, 14 100 and 38 700 cm^{-1} in the case of NTA complexes respectively.

The room temperature Mössbauer spectra gave the values of isomer shift and quadrupole splitting 0.20 and 0.35 respectively, which indicated the presence of iron in +3 state with high-spin distorted octahedral symmetry. This may be due to the presence of different types of ligands in the coordination sphere.

Phthalimide ion is a common constituent of complexes 1 to 4. The coordinating site of this ion can not be distinguished on the basis of their ir spectra because any change in the imide nitrogen which is directly linked to the carbonyl group will alter the molecular environment and hence the frequency of the latter even if it is not coordinated. However, on the basis of Lewis acid concept it may be established that the negatively charged imide nitrogen will have better possibilities of being coordinated than oxygen. There will be steric hindrance also if coordination is

through oxygen. Carbonyl stretching frequency was shifted from 1 750 to 1 710 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes which may be due to the mass effect. The band obtained at $\sim 3 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ in the spectrum of free phthalimide should disappear if coordination is through imide nitrogen but a broad band appeared in the spectra of the complexes at about the same frequency which may be due to coordinated water. The presence of coordinated water was inferred from the bands at 900, 750 and 650 cm^{-1} due to rocking, wagging and twisting modes of M-OH_2 unit.

The band of nitrilotriacetic acid at 1 670 cm^{-1} (COOH) shifted to 1 600 and 1 500 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the metal complexes (complex nos. 5–8) indicating the coordination of NTA through carboxylate groups. The ν_{CN} band is also observed generally in the same range, hence these frequencies may be due to the combined effect of COOH of NTA CN of oximes. The OH group of the oxime in case of all the complexes gave the stretching bands at around 3 400, 2 820 and 2 700 cm^{-1} . In view of the fact that free OH stretching vibrations appear near 3 600 cm^{-1} , this lowering of the band in the spectra of the complexes may be due to the formation of hydrogen bond or due to the combined effect of coordinated water and hydrogen bond in the case of complexes of sl. nos. 1, 2 and 3 (Table 1). These stretching bands were found absent in the spectrum of the complex of pyridine-2-aldoxime which also confirmed the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		Metal	C	H
1.	[Fe(Ph) ₃ (H ₂ SOx)(H ₂ O)]	8.53 (8.62)	56.80 (57.30)	2.07 (2.09)
2.	[Fe(Ph) ₃ (H ₂ FOX)(H ₂ O)]	8.00 (8.10)	55.30 (55.70)	2.70 (2.73)
3.	[Fe(Ph) ₃ (H ₂ BOx)(H ₂ O)]	7.65 (7.50)	60.10 (60.60)	3.42 (3.45)
4.	[Fe(Ph) ₃ (H ₂ POx)(H ₂ O)]	7.59 (7.60)	56.20 (56.70)	3.13 (3.15)
5.	K[Fe(NTA)(HSOx)]	13.36 (13.32)	36.90 (37.20)	2.83 (2.86)
6.	K[Fe(NTA)(HFOX)]	11.15 (11.12)	38.00 (38.20)	2.56 (2.58)
7.	K[Fe(NTA)(HBOx)]	10.72 (10.70)	45.50 (45.90)	3.22 (3.25)
8.	K[Fe(NTA)(HPOx)]	13.80 (13.76)	35.40 (35.60)	2.70 (2.72)

*Ph = C₈H₄O₂N; NTA = C₆H₆O₆N; H₂SOx = C₇H₇O₂N; H₂FOX = C₁₀H₈O₄N₂; H₂BOx = C₁₄H₁₂O₂N₂; H₂POx = C₆H₆ON₂.

NOTE

above observation. The bands due to ν_{NO} at 1 350, 1 200 and 1 000 cm^{-1} indicated the coordination of the oximes through nitrogen. The bands due to M-O and M-N were observed at around 300 and 600 cm^{-1} respectively.

In the case of first four complexes (Table 1), water molecule was removed on heating at about 150° which confirmed the presence of water molecule inside the coordination sphere.

Experimental

The physicochemical techniques used were the same as reported earlier¹⁷.

Potassium phthalimide was prepared by adding methanolic solution of potassium hydroxide into a saturated solution of phthalimide in methanol.

For preparing the complexes of sl. nos. 1-3 (Table 1), the solutions of ferric chloride and oxime in methanol and of potassium phthalimide in water were mixed in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 3. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath ~1 h. Dark brown precipitates formed on cooling were

washed with methanol and dried in a desiccant gel. In the case of complex of sl. no. 4 dimethylformamide was used as a solvent in place of methanol. In the case of complexes of sl. nos. 6-8, the aqueous solution of ferric chloride, nitrilotriacetic acid and oxime were mixed in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 1, and pH of the mixture was about 8.5 by adding aqueous KOH. The mixture was refluxed for ~2 h on a water-bath. The dark precipitates formed on cooling were washed with hot water and dried in an oven (~80°). In the case of complex of sl. no.7, dimethylformamide was used as solvent and mixture was concentrated by slow evaporation of the solvent till the crystals were formed.

Complexes of sl. nos. 1-4 were soluble in dimethylformamide and sl. nos. 5-8 in cold water.

References

1. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley-Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1976, pp. 51, 226.
2. C. L. SHARMA, K. J. SAMUEL, V. K. GARG and B. P. SINGH, *Hyperfine Interactions*, 1987, **35**, 887.